

PROMOTING OUTDOOR RECREATION THROUGH LANDSCAPE DESIGN OF NEGLECTED MINING PONDS IN JOS SOUTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, PLATEAU STATE

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Abstract: Recreation is a rewarding activity which an individual voluntarily participates in during leisure time to develop some skills which produce feelings of excitement, relaxation and satisfaction. This study explores the plausibility for transforming neglected mining ponds into vibrant recreational facilities ponds in Jos South LGA Plateau State. Through adaptive reuse strategies, the study aims to revitalize these areas, integrate them into the urban fabric as spaces for recreation and environmental restoration. This study adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative research methods. The study revealed that mining activities and erosion are the major contributors to the degraded landscape of the affected community. Hence the need for acute measures to be put in place as more and more mines lay waste and pose as a threat to health and the environment at large. This approach offers a roadmap for community dwellers, built environment professionals, and policymakers to reclaim these sites, turning them into assets that contribute to the social, economic, and environmental wellbeing of Jos Metropolis.

1.0 Introduction

Jos metropolis, Plateau State, Nigeria is historically known for its rich deposits of tin and other minerals, which fuelled extensive mining activities from the early 20th century. These activities were a significant part of the region's

economy but left behind numerous abandoned and neglected mining sites when the industry declined (Okunlola *et al.*, 2022). Over time, these sites have become eyesores, contributing to environmental degradation, including soil erosion, water pollution, and landscape

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disfigurement. The impact has led to most of the world's nations adopting regulations to moderate the negative effects of mining operations on the environment (Dagistanlı *et al.*, 2018). Interestingly, mining activities in the developed countries have since undergone phenomenal and rational changes within the purview of sustainable development (Bala *et al.*, 2021).

According to Atipo *et al.*, (2020) and Jibril *et al.*, (2022) mining of whatever form has a devastating impacts on the environment and is an impediment to Nigeria's vision of achieving a sustainable environment which is in line with the Sustainable Development Goal (SDGs) 15 (United Nations [UN], 2023), so that Nigeria will also conform to the global quest for developing nations sustainably. This pursuit encourages policies and programmes for concrete actions, social inclusion and the creation of an urban identity that give rise to maximum social ties (Jibril *et al.*, 2022). In view of this Dagistanlı *et al.*, (2018) and Wash *et al.*, (2022a) affirmed that there must be a healthy, rich and adequately protected environment in order to have a healthy, prosperous society.

It is worthy to note that some localities like, (Bukuru, Dorowa, Gero, Guut-Rayfield Kanar, Kuru Jantar, Ropp and Sabongida) in Jos South Local Government Area and (Bisichi, and Barkin Ladi communities) in Barkinladi Local Government Area of Plateau State, Nigeria still

experience varying environmental hazards posed by mining, where properties are poorly set out around the precinct of these pits (Yacim, 2013; Wapwera *et al.*, 2015; Abejide, 2021; Bala *et al.*, 2021; Ogunro & Owolabi, 2022). Furthermore, the extensive studies of Edun & Davou, 2013; Jaiye, (2013); Mallo & Wazoh (2014) Owonubi, (2017) and Jibril *et al.*, (2022) reveals the hazardous effects and impacts of mining to the immediate local residents include: loss of green vegetation of the region, altered landscapes, creation of mine spoils, unused pits and decrease in food production due to land degradation. Also high concentrations of toxic gases like methane, carbon monoxide, hydrogen and radioactive gases and presence of heavy metals (Pb, As, Cu, Cr and Ni), can accumulate in the abandoned mine ponds, making the use of the water hazardous to the locals who use it for irrigation and domestic purposes.

While the studies of Wapwera *et al.*, (2015) and Abejide, (2021) revealed that dozens of people have drowned in the deep unmanned ponds and there are speculations that the ponds have radioactive substances (X-ray, beta-ray and gamma-ray) as well as microbial contaminants which are major elements that have affected the health of the people and quality of their housing in the tin-mining region. Sati *et al.*, (2016) noted that the aesthetics of the built environment of Jos metropolitan areas is of poor quality as abandoned green spaces which would have enhanced the architectural

composition, are now refuse dump sites and habitats for mentally disabled persons. Hence, the need to reclaim these mining ponds especially those without any socio-economic values and turn them into vibrant recreational facilities.

Agreeing with the above assertion, Mwangi, (2015) pointed out that reclamation of post mining landscapes is a very challenging task since there is no unique reclamation planning scheme for such landscapes, and it highly depends on the site-specific characteristics. Most of these quarries are backfilled by dumping soil and waste which takes many years to refill. Natural approaches to reclamation may not apply for the long periods it takes, while human interventions takes many years to refill open pits depending on size and depth; this is even harder when we let nature to reclaim a site. It is for this reason that Dickson, (2014) and Ikpoku *et al.*, (2021) reiterated the importance of recreational activities, especially outdoors which contribute to the physical, economic and socio-cultural development of mankind. As posited by Ezeamaka & Oluwole, (2016) and Aboh *et al.*, (2021) there is the need for Nigerians to participate in recreation activities in order to improve their health, facilitate their economic output and also to make worthy use of leisure time. Their findings revealed that people who engage in physical activities such as walking, jogging, or swimming, schedule fewer office visits, maintain lower body fat

percentages, and have lower blood pressure and cholesterol levels.

Contextual to this paper, recreation is defined as a rewarding activity which an individual voluntarily participates in during leisure time to develop some skills which produce feelings of excitement, relaxation and satisfaction (Abbah & Okoro, 2021; Wash *et al.*, 2022b). Examples include: walking, swimming, reading, playing games, and dancing. In order to satisfy this need, usable parks, rivers, streams, coastline, lakes and playgrounds are needed. This increases the activities in which people desire to spend their increasing leisure hours.

Our Nigerian population and housing census figures (NPC, 2019), indicates that Greater Jos has a population of about 3,206,531 million, representing 43% of the total population of Plateau State, yet our green spaces (natural and amenity) have experienced more intense depletion in the past two decades largely due to increased anthropogenic activities that drive changes in land use and land cover with shortage of such facilities within the city (Sati *et al.*, 2016; Rikko *et al.*, 2022; Wash, *et al.*, 2021; & Wash *et al.*, 2022a). Meanwhile, the neglected mining sites, which occupy vast tracts of land, remain underutilized and pose safety and health risks to the surrounding communities. These sites, however, also hold historical and cultural significance, representing an important chapter in the region's industrial past.

There is a growing global trend toward the adaptive reuse of industrial sites, where old, abandoned spaces are creatively repurposed for new uses, often as recreational or cultural facilities. Successful projects that revitalized derelict areas, turning them into vibrant public spaces that benefit local communities both socially and economically include: Shimao Wonderland Intercontinental Hotel China, Karmiel Park Israel, Haller Park Kenya, Nairobi National Park, Kenya, Mines Resort City, kualar Lumpur, Malaysia, Collie Pit Lake District, Australia, Eden Project, United Kingdom, and Landschaftspark Duisburg-Nord, Germany (Mwangi, 2015). Given these challenges, there is a need to explore innovative approaches that address both the ecological degradation of mining ponds and the social well-being of surrounding communities. One promising pathway is the reclamation of these abandoned landscapes for outdoor recreation, a strategy that has been successfully implemented in various parts of the world.

2.0 Methodology

As posited by Goyol, (2019) research is an intensive activity that is based on the work of others and generating new ideas to pursue new questions and answers. This section describes the methodology used in this study. It describes the study location, the study area and methods chosen for this study. Moreover, this part explains the method of data collection, population of the study, and sample size.

2.1 Study Location: Jos South Local Government Area, Plateau State

Geographically, Jos South LGA covers a total area of 1,037 km². It lies between Latitude (9°34'22" and 9°54'40") N of the Equator and Longitude (8°39'55" and 8°59'13") E of the Prime Meridian, and with an average altitude of about 1280m above sea level (Figure 1). It has its headquarters in Bukuru, some 15 km from Jos, the state capital in the north-western portion of the state. The area is bounded in the Northwest by Bassa LGA, in the North by Jos North LGA, in the East by Jos East LGA, in the Southeast by Barkin Ladi LGA and Riyom LGA in the Southwest. It is the second most populated local government area in the state after Jos North. Du, Gyel, Kuru and Vwang are the four districts of Jos South (Bala *et al.*, 2021). According to Akintunde *et al.*, (2022); Folorunso *et al.*, (2023); and Owolabi *et al.*, (2024) the National Population census projected figure of the area was 493,818 for year 2020. With the human population density of 778 inhabitants/km², berom indigenes are the largest ethnic group in Jos South LGA in Plateau State, with Hausa Fulani, Yoruba, Igbos, and other tribes believed to have settled in the area during the mining boom. Furthermore, most of the dwellers of the studied area are engaged in mining and farming as the primary occupation.

Figure 1: Plateau State in National context and Jos Metropolis in State context leading to the study area in local context.

Source: Department of Geography and Planning, University of Jos, 2024

2.2 Study Area: Guut-Rayfield Jos-South LGA

The region, Guut-Rayfield lies between latitudes 09°50'49.4"N and longitude 008°55'00.8"E and occupies an area of 2.54 hectares (Figure 2). The population consists of middle and lower

class income earners. With this congestion a suitable recreation facility will help to solve problems relating to some social vices like drug abuse, kidnapping, armed robbery, juvenile delinquencies, etc. to mention but few.

Figure 2: Jos South Local Government Area in State context

Source: Department of Geography and Planning, University of Jos, 2024

2.3 Method of Data Collection

The study employed a multi-layered methodological approach to gather and analyze data relevant to the reclamation of mining ponds in Jos South LGA:

1. Field Survey & Site Reconnaissance:

Direct observations and photographic documentation were carried out to evaluate the existing physical conditions of the site. Soil characteristics, erosion patterns, and vegetation status were assessed to establish a baseline.

2. **Spatial Data Collection:** Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM) 30m elevation data was utilized to model topography

and hydrological flows. GIS tools were further employed to generate maps showing land use, cover types, and vulnerable zones requiring intervention (Figure 3)

3. Case Study Benchmarking:

Secondary data was collected on Mines Resort City, Kuala Lumpur (Malaysia), as a comparative case. Literature, design reports, and photographic evidence were reviewed to extract lessons applicable to the Jos context.

4. Community Input:

Informal interviews and interactions with local residents were conducted to capture perceptions of reclamation needs and preferred recreational

activities. These insights informed the inclusivity of the proposed design.

5. Design Conceptualization and Analysis:

Data from surveys, spatial mapping, case studies, and community input were 6.

synthesized into conceptual designs using Engler’s recycling approach. The design process involved iterative testing of circulation, land use zoning, and aesthetics to ensure environmental, social, and economic sustainability.

Figure 3: Base Map (Source: Authors ‘drawing, 2024).

3.0 Discussion of Findings

The findings are presented in five main sections. The first discusses the site analysis. The second is devoted to climate and vegetation, the focus on the third is design conceptualization. The fourth is on the planting scheme and specification while the fifth is devoted to the landscape maintenance plan.

3.1 Site Analysis

The study area has a mine pond which is characterized by stagnant water, indiscriminate dumping of wastes, stone quarrying, and cattle grazing (Plate i a & b). Mining activities has distorted the original topography of the site. The major baseline geology of the site is younger granites. Sheet, rills and gully erosion are a

major environmental problem on the site. An analysis chart was produced in (Table 1) to

depict existing conditions at study site.

Plate i a & b: Aerial view of abandoned mining pond

Source: Field work, 2024.

3.2 Climate and Vegetation

Human activities such as mining, stone blasting has greatly affected the land use and land cover of the site for a long period of time. Jos city has an equable climate with average monthly temperatures ranging between 21° and 25° C (69° and 77° F), average humidity of 60% and average annual rainfall of 1,400mm (56"). These average numbers however obscure substantial diurnal and seasonal variations which are of great significance in the design for

comfort and energy efficiency (Owonubi, 2017). The site falls largely within the northern guinea savannah zone which consists mainly of shrubs, grasses (see Plate ii a & b) and the plateau type of mosaic vegetation. Plants identified on the site included: Sweet bay (*Laurus nobilis*), Jasminum sambac (*Arabian jasminum*), common lantana (*Lantana camara*), cayenne snakeweed (*Stachytarpheta cavennensis*), Bur-mallow (*Urena lobata* L),

Plate ii a & b: Some existing native vegetation on granitic rock outcrop.

Source: Field work, 2024.

Table 1: Summary of Analysis Chart

S/No	Element	Quantity	Function	Opportunity	Constraint	Remark
1.	Main Entrance	1	Entry/Exit	Yes	None	Improve
2.	Pedestrian walkways	-	Circulation	Yes	None	Improve
3.	Rock outcrop	1	Outdoor sitting	Yes	None	Retained
4.	Mine Pond	1	Water body	Yes	None	Retained
5.	Tree	-	Provision of shade/Aesthetics/Erosion control	Yes	None	Retained & Introduced
6.	Shrubs	-	Provision of shade/Aesthetics/Erosion control	Yes	None	Retained & Introduced

Source: Field work, 2024.

3.3 Design Conceptualization

With the number of open mined ponds on the Jos Plateau, back filling will not be suitable. Rather restoration, mitigation, recycle and sustainable approaches to reclamation will be required for the majority of mining areas. An educative design approach works best for it creates awareness to all stakeholders on the negative effects if restoration plans are not implemented. From Engler's design approach, the author's used the recycling approach to create a landscape development for the study area. Integrative approach using design guidelines will be implemented to revive the grounds to a recreational facility. The design was conceptualized into different user groups based on gender, age and families. Developing suitable programs to cater for the needs of the various user groups. Three conceptual plans (with conceived spaces for reclamation) were developed using aesthetics, circulation, economy, and functionality. We believe the ideal conceptual plan will be developed fully by imputing required details and scale to bring it through an evolutionary process from concept to landscape master plan to resuscitate the degraded landscape to a sustainable design:

1. Conceptual Plan I – Green areas and outdoor sitting
2. Conceptual Plan II – Outdoor games/Children recreation area
3. Conceptual Plan III – Mini Zoo

3.3.1 Conceptual Plan I - Green areas and Outdoor sitting

The basic focus of this concept is to provide a serene environment for relaxation and recreation especially for middle age to people who are elderly. This conceptual plan is composed of the existing (Figure 4):

- a) mine pond which will be used for fishing purposes and provision will be made for a fish shop
- b) rock outcrops which will be converted to a rock garden with sit outs,
- c) designated relaxation spots and variety of shade trees, shrubs and ground covers. Trees recommended for quick vegetal cover of erosion sites include *Terminalia catappa* which has strong spreading roots that can hold the soil together. *Anacadium occidentale*, *Pinus caribaea*, *Eucalytus citriodora*, *Acioa barteri*, *Oxytenanthera abyssinica*, *Bambus vulgaris*, *Dacryodes edulis*. Exotic species certified good as efficient green manure crops include *Leucaena leucocephala*, *Gliricidia sepium* (Etukudo, 2000).
- d) Water plants would be planted along the mine ponds and in marshy areas of the study area Examples of water plants to be used include water purslane, waterweed plants, African water fern plant, and Anubias. Some of the best floating water plants on ponds are duckweed and the mosaic flower, water lilies, lotus, water hawthorn plants, and mosaic flower.

Figure 4: Conceptual Plan I

Scale: To sketch, (Source: Authors' drawing, 2024)

3.3.2 Conceptual Plan II - Outdoor games/Children recreation area

The main focus of this concept is to create recreational facilities for children basically within the age group of three to fifteen years of age. This second conceptual plan is composed of the existing (Figure 5):

- a) Children recreation area with variety of games (indoor and outdoor) which include swings, slides, bouncing castles and a merry-go-round etc.
- b) rock outcrops with facilities for exciting activities

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c) other proposals include a mini pond where mini boating activities can take place,

Figure 5: Conceptual Plan II

Scale: To sketch, (Source: Authors’ drawing, 2024)

3.3.3 Conceptual Plan III – Mini Zoo

The mini zoo concept is to provide a conducive environment for selected animals that are not harmful to humans to thrive on free range. While at the same time making the

environment exciting for tourists. Specialized animal cages would be erected mainly for breeding purposes. The third conceptual plan is composed of the existing (Figure 6):

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a) mine pond around which the habitat for aquatic animals will be developed. Some of these animals include pond snails, turtles, ducks, swans. In addition, the pond can be stocked with small, inoffensive fish varieties, including Platies (*P. variatus*), Paradise Fish (*Macropodus opercularis*), Florida Blue-fin Killiefish (*Leucania goodei*), and Persian Killiefish (*Aphanius mento*), among others.

b) rock outcrops, for animals like beaver, squirrel, antelopes and tortoise just to mention a few.

c) Trees and shrubs would be planted for attracting various bird species: These will

include amongst many the oak, willows, cherries, Juniper, and black berry.

d) Furthermore, fruit trees would be planted for the enclosure for animals like monkeys.

Figure 6: Conceptual Plan III

Scale: To sketch, (Source: Authors’ drawing, 2024)

4.0 Planting Scheme and Specifications

Planting scheme is the art of installation and spacing of plants around the centre, (Acquaah, 2009) this is meant to provide an aesthetical appeal and enhance circulation

within the environment (Table 2). At this stage, plants are introduced to their appropriate locations based on the planting scheme. Watering is done afterwards and carried out during the dry season.

Table 2: Planting Scheme and Specifications

S/N	Common Name	Botanical Name	Max Height(M)	Spread(M)	Spacing (M)	Qty	Use
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Lawn grass	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> <i>Axonopus compressus</i> <i>Zoysia tennifolia</i> <i>Polytrias praemorsa</i>	0.1	-	-	-	Lawn
Alternanthera	<i>Alternanthera spp</i>	0.5	0.5	0.2	50	Ground Cover
Eucalyptus	<i>Euclalyptus spp</i>	10	6	4	25	Shelterbelt
Teak	<i>Tectona grandis</i>	20	6	4	25	Shelterbelt
Jacaranda	<i>Jacaranda filicifolia</i>	12	6	4	10	Shade
Araucaria	<i>Araucaria heterophylla</i>	8	2.5	-	10	Specimen
Agave	<i>Agave americana</i>	2	2	3	10	Specimen
Albizia	<i>Albizia lebbek</i>	3	3	2	15	Specimen
Queen of the night	<i>Cestrum nocturnum</i>	3	6	4	20	Scent plant
Roses	<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i>	1.5	1.2	1	20	Scent plant
Aquatic plants	<i>Specified in plan</i>	0.8	0.5	0.2	50	Ornamental
Morning glory	<i>Ipomea learil</i>	-	-	-	10	Cripping
Africa never die	<i>Targetis erecta</i>	0.2	0.5	0.2	50	Bedding
Indian shots	<i>Cana indica</i>	0.2	0.5	0.2	50	Bedding
Green oleander	<i>Cascabela thevetia</i>	3.5	2	0.5	50	Border
Jos private	<i>Lantana camara</i>	3.6	0.4	1.5	50	Border plant
Sun flower	<i>Helianthus annus</i>	1.8	0.5	0.2	25	Bloom
Indian blood	<i>Prunus persica</i>	1.8	0.5	0.2	25	Bloom
Conifers (yellow)	<i>Chamaecyparis obtusa</i>	12	3	3	50	Avenue
Begonia	<i>Begonia obliqua</i>	0.2	0.5	0.2	50	Hedge

	Pictum	<i>Athyrium niponicum</i>	2	1.8	1	100	Hedge
	Chrysanthemums	<i>Chrysanthemums spp</i>	0.1	0.5	0.2	50	Hedge
	Oleander	<i>Nerium oleander</i>	2.5	2	0.5	100	Hedge
	Acalypha	<i>Acalypha spp</i>	3.6	0.4	1.5	100	Hedge
	Pictum	<i>Athyrium niponicum</i>	2	1.8	1	100	Hedge
	Ixora	<i>Ixora coccinea</i>	2	2.5	2	50	Hedge
	Euonymus	<i>Euonymus spp</i>	1.2	1.2	0.5	50	Hedge
	Croton	<i>Codiaecum variegatum</i>	1.2	1.8	1	100	Hedge
	Yellow bush	<i>Duranta rupen</i>	1.2	1.2	0.5	100	Hedge
a	Thuja	<i>Thuja plicata</i>	8	3	2	40	Shrub
	Terminalia	<i>Terminalia mantaly</i>	20	3.5	4	40	Shrub
	Pine	<i>Pinus caribae</i>	4	3	3	20	Shrub

Source: Authors' construct, (2024)

5.0 Landscape Maintenance Plan

Maintenance is the work undertaken in order to keep, restore or improve a facility. Lack of proper maintenance of a facility or building leads to rapid dilapidation of the facility or building (Acquaah, 2009). Maintenance activities are activities meant to keep the environment beautiful and pleasing. These activities include: watering, mowing, fertilizer application, staking, weeding, pesticide application, mulching and provision of mechanical support (Table 3).

5.1 Watering

Acquaah (2009) defined watering as wetting of the soil surface. Watering is a landscape maintenance activity that is frequently

performed improperly making the aim not to be achieved. Effective watering requires that water be delivered in adequate amounts to the root zone of plants. The following are the ways of watering that will be applied efficiently in maintaining the plants

- i. Hand watering, using a watering can
- ii. Use of sprinklers
- iii. The use of water hose

For effective result after watering all planted elements is to be watered at early stage at an interval of one day, before 10 a.m. and at about 6 p.m. when temperatures are cooler and the air is calmer so that evaporation is kept to a minimum.

5.2 Mulching

Mulching offers several advantages over clean cultivation (no mulch). The mulch material to

be used for this project is sugarcane and grass straw. As the mulch decomposed, it adds to the fertility of the soil, organic reaction and composition. Place mulch around the new plant in a circle that is 18–24 inches diameter and 2–3 inches thick. Pull the mulch away from direct contact with the trunk of any trees to prevent decay. If plantings are placed in a bed, mulch the entire bed to a depth of 2–3 inches, also keeping mulch away from the trunk of trees and larger shrubs. And pruning is the pathway to long life for most plants.

5.3 Fertilizer Application

Ornamental plants require nutrients for healthy growth. Soils that are not well fertilized contain sufficient plant nutrients (Acquaah, 2009). The recommended nutritional value for the plants in this environment is either cow dung or poultry

waste (inorganic fertilizer) knowing that nutrients are a major environmental requirement necessary for the survival, growth and development of all plants this inorganic fertilizer is the major nutritional substance that will be added to the plant in a space of 2 – 3-months interval.

5.4 Pruning

Pruning is practice involving the selective removal of parts of plant, such as branches, buds, or roots. Reasons for pruning include deadwood removal, bloom, shape and size, to encourage growth etc. Shrubs often cannot go without pruning if they are to serve their intended purpose in the landscape. Except for a few dwarfs or extremely slow-growing plants, prune all shrubs regularly or as needed usually every year or two.

Table 3: Phasing Programme for Maintenance Schedule

Operations	January				February				March				April				May				June			
Week	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
Irrigation	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*								
Lawns - Mowing												*						*		*		*		*
Weeding												*								*				
Blooms – replanting																		*						

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2030. This necessitates the following recommendations:

1. There is need to develop and implement awareness programs to affected communities on the hazardous effects and impacts of mining.
2. More land reclamation, restoration, and management strategies that ensures land availability for various economic uses is recommended.
3. The State Government should establish a supervisory and regulatory framework to mitigate the impacts of tin-mining exploitation and exploration activities on the environment. Also, those that breach the rule should be prosecuted.

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